

Renewable Energy the Bed Rock of Power Stability in Nigeria (A Case Study of Wind Turbine)

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Received: September 2, 2014, Accepted: October 7, 2014, Published: October 7, 2014.

ABSTRACT

This paper discussed renewable energy the bed rock of power stability in Nigeria with wind turbine as a reference point. Vertical wind turbine was worked upon relevant mathematical analysis on wind turbine construction and design were carried out, analysis on wind density, power generated, from the wind turbine, kinetic energy in air, solidity of the wind turbine and area of the blades were also analyzed. This paper also deals with various types of wind turbine and specific attention was on Vertical wind turbine, with other types of wind turbine in this research such as Modern wind turbine, Horizontal wind turbine. It was found that in our geographical area the vertical wind turbine is better, after various calculations and analysis were carried out on the various wind turbine that were researched upon.

Keyword: Turbine, Induction Motor, Mechanical Coupling, Energy, Frictionless Bearings, Gears.

INTRODUCTION

Since ancient times wind has been exploited in different ways, mainly for grain milling and water pumping. With the advent of the industrial era, wind energy has gradually been replaced by fossil fuels. The windmills bring practical relegated to pump water for agricultural use in the 20th century, new designs enabled electricity generation at small scale levels for battery charging uses.

After the early 1970's oil crisis, wind technology experienced a revolution, motivated by the oil price boost, many countries promoted ambitious wind energy research and development programme. As a result, new materials and modern turbine designs were developed, initiating the age of large scale wind electricity generation. "Unpublished" [1].

During the last decades, the increasing concern about the environment and the trends towards the diversification of the energy market have been reinforcing the interest in wind energy exploitation. Nowadays, wind energy is by far the fastest growing renewable energy resource. The progress of wind power around the world in recent years has exceeded all expectations, with Europe leading the global market in numbers. The wind turbine capacity installed in Europe increased during the last years at an annual growth rate of 30. "Unpublished" [1].

The wind energy industry so-far has been supported by market incentives backed by government policies on sustainable energy resources. The cost of electricity provided by wind power facilities has been dropping drastically since the 1980's. These cost reductions are due to new technologies and higher production scales leading to larger, more efficient and more reliable wind turbine [3].

A wind turbine is a rotating machine which converts the kinetic energy of wind into mechanical energy. If the mechanical energy

is used directly by machinery, such as a pump or grinding stone, the machine is usually called a windmill. If the mechanical energy is instead converted to electricity, the machine is called a wind generator, wind turbine, wind power unit (WPU), wind energy converter (WEC) or aero generator. Wind machines were used in Persia as early as 200 B.C, the wind wheel of Heron of Alexandria marks one of the first known instances of wind powering a machine in history. However, the first practical windmills were built in Sistan, Iran, from the 7th century. These were vertical axle windmills which had long vertical driveshafts with rectangle shaped blades made of six to twelve sails covered in reed matting or cloth material, these wind mills were used in the gristmilling and sugarcane industries [1,2,5].

By the 14th century, Dutch windmill were in use to drain of the Rhine River Delta. In Denmark by 1900, there were about 2500 wind mills for mechanical loads such as pumps and mills, producing an estimated combined peak power of about 30MW. The first known electricity generating wind mill operated was a battery charging machine installed in 1887 by James Blyth in Scotland.

The first windmill for electricity production in the United States was built in Cleveland, Ohio by Charles F. Bush in 1888, and in 1908 there were 72 wind driven electric generators from 5Kw to 25KW. The largest machines were on 24m (79ft) towers with four blade 23m (75ft) diameter rotors. Around the time of world war I, American windmill makers were producing 100,000 farm windmill each year, mostly for water pumping by the 1930's windmills for electricity were common on farms, mostly in the United states where distribution systems had not yet been installed in this period high tensile steel was cheap, and windmills were placed atop prefabricated open steel lattice towers [6].

A forerunner of modern horizontal axis wind generators was in service at Yalta, USSR in 1931. This was a 100KW generator on a 30m (100ft) tower, connected to the local 6.3KV distribution system. It was reported to have an annual capacity factor 32 percent, not much different from current wind machines in the fall of 1941, the first mega watt class wind turbine was synchronized to utility grid in Vermont. The Smith-Putnan wind turbine only ran for 1100 hours. Due to war time material shortages the unit was not repaired.

The first utility grid connected wind turbine operated in the UK was built by John Brown and company in 1954 in the Orkney Islands, it had an 18 meter diameter, three-bladed rotor and a rated output of 100KW [3].

A yardstick frequently used to determine good location is referred to as wind power Density (WPD) it is a calculation relating the effectiveness force of the wind at a particular location, frequently expressed in terms of the elevation above ground level over a period of time. It takes into account the wind velocity and mass.

Types of turbine (WIND)

Horizontal wind turbine:

Wind turbines can rotate about either a horizontal or vertical axis with respect to the tower, the horizontal-axis wind turbine (HAWT) have the main rotor shaft and electrical generator at the top of a tower, and must be pointed into the wind. Small turbines are pointed by a simple wind vane, while large turbines generally use a wind sensor coupled with a servo motor. Most have a gearbox, which turns the slow rotation of the blades into a quicker rotation that is more suitable to drive an electrical generator.

Since a tower produces turbulence behind it, the turbine is usually pointed upwind of the tower. Turbine blades are made stiff to prevent the blades from being pushed into the tower by high winds. Additionally, the blades are placed a considerable distance in front of the tower and are sometimes tilted forward into the wind a small amount.

Downwind machines has been built, despite the problem of turbulence (Mast Wake) because they don't need an additional mechanism for keeping them in line with the wind, and because in high winds the blades can be allowed to bend which reduces their swept area and thus their wind resistance. Since cyclic (that is repetitive) turbulence may lead to fatigue failures most HAWTs are upwind machines.

Horizontal subtypes

These squat structures, typically (at least) four bladed, usually with wooden shuttles or fabric sails, were developed in Europe. These windmills were pointed into the wind manually or via a tail fan and were typically used a grind grain. In the Netherlands they were also used to pump water from low lying land and were instrumental in keeping its polders dry. In Schiedam, the Netherlands, a traditional style windmill (the Noletmolen) was built in 2005 to generate electricity, the mill is one of the tallest mills in the world being some 42.5 meters 9139 ft) tall.

The eclipse windmill factory was set up around 1866 in Beloit, Wisconsin and soon because successful building mills for pumping water on farms and for filling railroad tanks. Other firms like star, Dempster and Aeromotor also entered the market. Hundreds of thousands of these mills were produced before rural

electrification and small numbers continue to be made. They typically had many blades, operated at tip speed ratios not better than one, and had good starting torque. Some had small direct current generators used to charge storage batteries, to provide power to lights, or operate a radio receiver.

The American rural electrification connected many farms to centrally generated power and replaced individual windmills as a primary source of farm power by the 1950s. They were also produced in other countries like South Africa and Australia (where an American design was copied in 1876).such devices are still used in locations where it is too costly to bring in commercial power.

Modern wind turbines

Turbines used in wind farms for commercial production of electricity (electric power) are usually three bladed and pointed into the wind by computer - controlled motors. These have high tip speeds of over 320km/h (200 miles per hour), high efficiency, and low torque ripple, which contribute to good reliability. The blades are usually coloured light gray to blend in with the clouds and range in length from 20 – 40 meters (65 to 130ft) or more. The tubular steel towers range from 60 to 90 meters (65 to 130ft) or more. The tubular steel towers range from 60 to 90 meters (200 to 300ft) tall. The blades rotate at 10-22 revolutions per minute. At 22 rotations per minute the tip speed exceeds 300ft per second. A gear box is commonly used to set up the speed generator, although designs may also use direct drive of an annular generator. Some models operate at constant speed, but more energy can be collected by variable speed turbines which use a solid state power converter to interface to the transmission system. All turbines are equipped with shut down features to avoid damage at high wind speed.

Advantage of horizontal wind turbines

Variable blade pitch which gives the turbine blades the optimum angle of attack. Allowing the angle of attack to be remotely adjusted gives greater control, so the turbine collects the maximum amount of wind energy for the time of day and season. The tall base allows access to stronger wind in sites with shear. In some wind shear sites, every ten meters up, the wind speed can increase by 20% and the power output by 34%. High efficiency, since the blades always moves perpendicularly to the wind, receiving power through the whole rotation. In contrast, all vertical axis wind turbines designs, involves various types of reciprocating actions, requiring airfoil surfaces to back track against the wind for part of the cycle. Backtracking against the wind leads to inherently lower efficiency. The face of a horizontal axis blade is struck by the wind at consistent angle regardless of the position in its rotation. This result in a consistent lateral wind loading over the course of a rotation, reducing vibration and audible noise couples to the tower or mount.

Cyclic stresses and vibration

Cyclic stresses fatigue and blade axis and bearing resulting in material failures that were a major cause of turbine failure for many years. Because wind the wind direction is highly variable with a vertical axis, the generator and gear box can be placed near the ground, so the tower doesn't need to support it, and it is more accessible for maintenance.

It is difficult to mount vertical axis turbines on towers, meaning they are often installed nearer to the base on which they rest, such

as the ground or a building rooftops. The wind speed is slower at a lower altitude, so less wind energy is available for a given size turbine. Airflow near the ground and other objects can create turbulent flow, which can maintain or shorten the service life. However, when a turbine is mounted on a rooftop, the building generally redirects wind over the roof and these can double the wind speed at the turbine. If the height of the rooftop mounted turbine tower is approximately 50% of the building height, this is near the optimum or maximum wind energy and minimum wind turbulence.

Vertical axis subtypes Darrieus wind turbine

“Eggbeater” turbines or Darrieus turbines velocity often increases at higher altitudes, the backward the force and torque on a horizontal – axis wind turbine (HAWT) blade peaks as it turns through the highest point in its circle. The tower hinders the airflow at the lowest point in the circle, which produces a local dip in force and torque. These effects produce a cyclic twist on the main bearings of a HAWT. The combined twist is worst in machines with an even number of blades, where one is straight up when another is straight down. To improve reliability, teetering hubs have been used which allow the main shaft to rock through a few degrees, so that the main bearings do not have to resist the torque peaks.

The rotating blades of a wind turbine act like a gyroscope. As it pivots along its vertical axis to face the wind, gyroscope precession tries to twist the turbine disc along its horizontal axis. For each blade on a wind generator’s turbine, processive force is at a minimum when the blade is horizontal and at a maximum when the blade is vertical. Vertical – axis wind turbine have the main rotor shaft arranged vertically, key advantages of this arrangement are that the turbine does not need to be pointed into the wind to be effective.

This is an advantage on sites where bending stresses straight, V, or curved blades may be used.

Vertical axis wind turbine advantages

A massive tower structure is less frequently used, as VAWTS are more frequently mounted with the lower bearing mounted near the ground.

Designs without yaw mechanisms are possible with fixed pitch rotor designs. The generator of a VAWT can be located nearer the ground, making it easier to maintain the moving parts.

VAWTs have lower wind setup speeds than HAWTs. Typically, they start creating electricity at 6 m.p.h. (10km/h). VAWTs may be built at locations where taller structures are prohibited. CAWTs situated close to the ground can take advantage of locations where mesas, hilltops, ridgelines, and passes funnel the wind and increase wind velocity. VAWTs may have a lower noise signature.

Vertical axis wind turbine disadvantages

A VAWT that uses guy – wires to hold it in place puts stress on the bottom bearing as all the weight of the rotor is on the bearing. Guy wires attached to the top bearing increase downward thrust in wind gusts. Solving this problem requires a superstructure to hold a top bearing in place to eliminate the downward thrusts of gust event in guy wired models.

The stress in each blade due to wind loading changes since twice during each revolution as the apparent wind direction moves

through 360 degrees. This reversal of the stress increases the likelihood of blade failure by fatigue. While VAWTs components are located on the ground, they are also located under the weight of the structure above it. Which can make changing out parts very difficult without dismantling the structure, if not designed properly.

Having rotors located close to the ground where wind speeds are lower due to the ground’s surface drag, VAWTs may not produce as much energy at a given site as a HAWT with the same footprint or height. Were named after the French Inventor, Georges Darrieus, they have good efficiency, but produce large torque ripple and cyclical stress on the tower, which contributes to poor reliability. They also generally require some external power source, or an additional sevonius rotor to start turning, because the starting torque is very low. The torque ripple is reduced by using three or more blades which results in a higher solidity for the rotor. Solidity is measured by blade area divided by the rotor area. Newer Darrieus type turbines are not hold up by gay-wines but have an external superstructure connected to the top bearing.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Wind power density

Calculating wind speed at one height, if it is known at another height, we can use.

$$\vec{V}_2 = \vec{V}_1 \left(\frac{h_2}{h_1} \right)^n \quad 1.0$$

Where n the ground surface friction coefficient and takes on different values according to the nature of the terrain.

NB: City downtown: n = 0.4

$$V_1 = 2.135 \text{ m/s}$$

$$h_1 = 25\text{m}, h_2 = 15.52\text{m} \therefore h_2 \simeq 16\text{m}$$

Substituting the data into equation (1.0) above we have

$$\vec{V}_2 = 2.135 \left(\frac{16}{25} \right)^{0.4}$$

$$\vec{V}_2 = 2.135 (0.64)^{0.4}$$

$$\vec{V}_2 = 2.135 \times 0.8365$$

$$\vec{V}_2 = 1.78595$$

$$\vec{V}_2 = 1.786 \text{ m/s}$$

For the air density we will use the ideal gas law

$$\rho = \frac{P}{RT} \quad 1.1$$

$$\rho = \frac{101}{(8.314/29)(298)}$$

$$\rho = 1.18 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

Power generated from the wind turbine

$$\text{Rotor diameter} = 106\text{mm}$$

$$\text{Blade length} = 2.5\text{m}$$

$$\text{Speed of wind} = 1.786\text{m/s}$$

$$\text{Speed of motor} = 1400 \text{ rpm}$$

(Source: Design of Wind Turbine carried out)

The power formula will be given as

$$\dot{W}_{wt} = \int_{wt} \frac{1}{2} \rho A \bar{V}^3 \quad 1.2$$

Where;

$$\rho = 1.18 \text{ kg} / \text{m}^3$$

$$A = D_{\text{rotor}} L_{\text{blade}} = 106 \times 2.5 = 265 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\bar{V}^3 = 1.786 \text{ m} / \text{s}$$

The efficiency will come from the tip speed ratio (TSR) equation which is given as

$$TSR = \frac{WR_{\text{rotor}}}{\bar{V}}$$

$$TSR = \frac{(1400/60)(2\pi)(106/2)}{1.786} \quad 1.3$$

$$TSR = \frac{7.770.20583}{1.786}$$

$$TSR = 4.350$$

Since we are using a three blade wind turbine, the appropriate efficiency equation is given as;

$$\int_{wt} = -0.020554(TSR)^2 + 0.18327(TSR) + 0.023286 \quad 1.4$$

$$\int_{wt} = -0.020554(4.350)^2 + 0.18327(4.350) + 0.023286$$

$$\int_{wt} = 0.432$$

Substituting into equation (3.3) to get the power

$$\dot{W}_{wt} = \int_{wt} \rho A \bar{V}^3$$

$$\dot{W}_{wt} = 0.432 \times \frac{1}{2} \times 1.18 \times 265 \times 1.786^3$$

$$\dot{W}_{wt} = 384.79 \text{ kw}(w)$$

K. Kinetic energy in air

$$K.E = \frac{1}{2} MV^2 \quad 1.5$$

Where;

$$M = \text{Mass, Assume } m = 4$$

$$V = \text{Velocity} = 1.786$$

Substituting into equation (1.5) above

$$K.E = \frac{1}{2} \times 4 \times (1.786)^2$$

$$K.E = 6.38 \text{ j}$$

Solidity

This is usually defined as the percentage of the circumference of the rotor which is filled by rotor blade. A 0.15 meter diameter rotor has 3 blades each 0.1 meter wide. Its solidity is calculator as

$$\text{Solidity} = \frac{3 \times 0.1}{\pi \times 106} \times 100 = 9\%$$

The greater the solidity of the rotor the slower it needs to turn to intercept the wind. A two or three blade turbine has a very low solidity and therefore need to rotate quickly to intercept the wind. Otherwise a lot of wind energy would be lost through the large gaps between the blades.

The general formula is given as.

$$\text{solidity}\% = 31.8 \times \text{No. of blades} \times \text{bladewidth} \div \text{Rotor diameter} \quad 1.6$$

let's say one has a large air parcel with the shape of a huge hockey puck:

that is, it has the geometry of a collection of air molecules passing through the plane of a wind turbine's blades (which sweep out a cross-sectional area **A**), with thickness (**D**) passing through the plane over a given time.

Area of blade

$$A = \pi L^2 \text{ blade} \quad 1.7$$

$$A = \pi \times 2.5^2$$

$$A = 19.63$$

CONCLUSION

This Research work on wind turbine was executed and after test the design met specification. However, the general operation of the device including performance is dependent on the user.

The construction was done in such a way that it makes maintenance easy and affordable for the user should there be system breakdown.

This research work uses induction motor in the construction of wind turbine.

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Citation: Emmanuel .I. Okhueleigbe et all., (2014) Renewable Energy the Bed Rock of Power Stability in Nigeria (A Case Study of Wind Turbine). J. of Advancement in Engineering and Technology. V2I1. DOI: 10.15297/JAET.V2I1.01

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